

Purposeful utilization of digital learning and teaching

Kirsi-Maria Rinneheimo¹, Daniela Velichová², Ion Mierlus Mazilu³, David Luengo Garcia⁴

¹*Mathematics and Physics, Tampere University of Applied Sciences, Finland*

²*Institute of Mathematics and Physics, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia*

³*Department of Mathematics and Computers Science, Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest, Romania*

⁴*Department of Signal Theory and Communications, Technical University of Madrid, Spain*

Abstract

In teaching technical subjects, it is important to get students to actively engage and build conceptually accurate basic images related to technical subjects. Pedagogically well-implemented teaching can also reduce dropouts and increase the attractiveness of learning. Various digital methods also increase accessibility, benefitting students with learning difficulties and, helping teachers meet the needs of diverse groups. This article presents the DigiSTEM Erasmus+ project that aimed to increase digital and pedagogical competence of HEI educators and the availability of digital resources in STEM subjects. By increasing such competences of educators, it should give them tools and knowledge to produce and implement digital resources and activities for different personalised learning scenarios in pedagogically meaningful ways. The project developed and disseminated digital learning resources and methodologies, promoting active and self-regulated learning using educational technology and learning analytics.

Introduction

The field of digital education is changing rapidly, which is why it must be continuously studied, and the competences of the educators require continuous development and updating. Also, the Digital Education Action Plan set by the Commission has a priority to make better use of digital technology for teaching and learning. Different educational research studies (Deák & Kumar, 2024; Rahman, 2024) have highlighted that educators have an inadequate competence regarding effective use of digital tools and resources in education from both pedagogical and technological perspectives. Barriers such as lack of confidence, competence, and access to resources continue to hinder the integration of digital methods in education (Santoveña-Casal & Rodríguez López, 2024). Research has shown that students would like to use digital learning possibilities and methods more widely in STEM courses (i.e. Rinneheimo et al., 2018; Kinnari-Korpela & Suhonen, 2017, Santoveña-Casal & Rodríguez López, 2024). However, utilizing educational technology in STEM subjects is very limited and it lags behind the expectations, even though using instructional design that utilizes educational technologies has a great and recognized potential to increase students' motivation, the attractiveness of the subject, and to promote active learning and improve learning outcomes (e.g. Kinnari-Korpela, 2019; Kinnari-Korpela & Suhonen, 2017).

The Erasmus+ funded three-year DigiSTEM project (2021-2024), “Promoting Digital Learning in STEM Subjects,” aimed to increase the digital and pedagogical competence of HEI educators and the availability of digital resources in STEM subjects (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). By increasing such competences of educators, it should give them tools and knowledge to produce and implement digital resources and activities for different personalised learning scenarios in pedagogically meaningful ways.

This article presents the main outcomes of the DigiSTEM project. The objective of the project was to increase the digital and pedagogical competence of HEI educators and the availability of digital resources in STEM subjects on a large scale to achieve long-lasting effects in everyday activity in European HEIs. The objective was to build HEI educators' competence of such instructional design that improves students' active learning, self-regulated learning and learning engagement with the help of educational technology and learning analytics to provide more effective and personalised support of learners. By increasing such competences of educators, it should give them tools and knowledge to produce and implement digital resources and activities (e.g. learning analytics, digital languages, screencasts, visualisations, and intelligent assessment) for different personalised learning scenarios in pedagogically meaningful ways. This is expected to increase digital competence and skills among the students, to motivate and engage students. The focus was on the combination of pedagogics and technology. In the next section we briefly recap the implementation of the project. We then describe the principal results, advertise the Moodle DigiSTEM platform that is available free on-line and draw some conclusions for the STEM education of engineers.

Implementation

To address the growing need for digital transformation in higher education, the DigiSTEM project equipped educators with the tools and knowledge to design and implement digital learning resources and activities—tailored to diverse and personalized learning scenarios in pedagogically meaningful ways.

The DigiSTEM project consortium consisted of four university partners: Tampere University of Applied Sciences (Finland), Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (Slovakia), Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest (Romania) and Technical University of Madrid (Spain). The project brought together the skills and knowledge, as well as best practices, of several HEI educators, both of STEM subjects but also educators of online pedagogy and combined their expertise into creating the learning resources. On one hand, the STEM educators had the latest knowledge of both the technology that could be introduced in the learning resources and also the needs of their peer educators, and on the other hand, the pedagogical experts were able to offer new, perhaps not previously utilised, viewpoints into online education. While STEM educators contributed subject-specific knowledge and insight into the practical needs of their peers, pedagogical experts introduced innovative approaches to digital teaching and learning, particularly in fostering student engagement and self-regulated learning.

The project implemented the DigiSTEM methodology, which encapsulates innovative pedagogies, best practices, and concrete examples for implementing digital learning and teaching of STEM and similar subjects. Following this methodology, the project planned and produced learning materials for STEM educators and has published two Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) on the Moodle platform:

- *Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally*
- *Pedagogy for Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally*

The materials were created by STEM educators from each of the partners, and further modified by experts in accessibility in order to make them more useful for different types of learners. The courses were designed by STEM educators from each partner, which ensured the quality of the created learning resources and their suitability specifically for HEI STEM educators. The material creators also included experts in online pedagogy, who implemented pedagogical learning resources regarding online education and student involvement, with an especial focus on teaching students to take responsibility for their own learning. The learning resources consist of a rich variety of formats - text, videos, images and interactive materials, as well as examples and several practical demonstrations and instructions on how the users may utilise mathematical software in their educational activities, digital assessment tools, and active learning strategies. All the learning resources have been published on-line using a Creative Commons licence, making them freely available via the DigiSTEM platform and DigiCampus Moodle for any STEM teacher interested in the topics. This open-access approach ensures that any interested STEM educator can benefit from the materials, supporting the broader goal of enhancing digital competence across European higher education institutions.

Project outputs

The main concrete outputs were the creation of two online learning courses (MOOCs) on the Moodle platform for STEM educators: *Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally* and *Pedagogy for Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally*. The courses have been published on-line on the DigiSTEM Platform and DigiCampus Moodle, using the CC-licence, making them freely available for any STEM teacher interested in the topics. Both courses can be found as follows:

- via the project's website (<https://webpages.tuni.fi/stem> or digistem.eu)
- on DigiCampus (<https://digicampus.fi>)

These MOOCs were designed to support the professional development of higher education STEM educators by providing high-quality, research-informed digital learning resources. Below is a brief overview of each course:

- Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally

This course is specifically designed to enhance the skills and knowledge of STEM teachers, lecturers, and professors in using digital tools and resources.

The course consists of micro modules about the following topics:

- Using Technology in Teaching and Learning
- Learning Environments for STEM Teaching
- Top Tools for Learning and Teaching
- Videos on Teaching and Learning
- Learning Analytics
- AI Tools
- Find Innovative Tools for Chemistry and Physics: Digital Modeling
- STACK
- Mathematics Software, GeoGebra, LaTeX, Wolfram Mathematica

This course is specifically designed to enhance the skills and knowledge of STEM teachers, lecturers, and professors in using digital tools and resources. Available micro modules bring a comprehensive overview of the best digital and online educational tools for enhanced learning experiences, basic information on how to introduce specific tools in STEM subjects with several examples of the best practice. Instructions on how to design and create their own digital materials as interactive applets, educational videos or simulations are readily available for use. Learning analytics and how they can be used to prevent students from dropping out of courses is presented in separate module. A detailed description of STACK as a system for computer-aided assessment (CAA) in mathematics and how to use it to create efficient and even time-saving exercises is also available. A separate module on AI and its utilisation in university education is also included with links to sites providing current information on this “hot” topic. Teachers of STEM subjects Physics or Chemistry might find here many inspirational educational videos, simulations and other materials. A general overview of some popular free mathematical software packages GeoGebra, Wolfram Mathematica and Latex, pointing to their key features and capabilities is presented with numerous examples.

- **Pedagogy for Teaching STEM Subjects Digitally**

This course is specifically designed to develop the pedagogical competences of teachers/lecturers/professors of STEM subjects in higher education institutions.

The course consists of micro modules about the following topics:

- Best Pedagogical Practices of STEM Teachers
- Active Learning and EduScrum Active Learning Method
- Self-Regulation
- Assessment
- New Trends in Teaching Engineering Mathematics
- The Use of Mathematical Software in Teaching

The course is composed of independent modules, so it is free to choose to complete the topics that are interesting and useful for the individual users’ needs. Various active

learning methods are presented with information on how to introduce them within the specific educational scenarios in order to activate students and enhance their motivation and understanding. The EduScrum method promoting cooperation of small groups of 4-5 students is described in detail, as one of the most appreciated and best suited methods from the perspective of the students themselves. Methods to promote students' self-regulated study approach and learning are described, while several ideas on how to proceed in applying these methods are suggested. Quite a lot of ideas might be found in the module dealing with assessment. Traditional and innovative methods of testing and verifying acquired knowledge are analysed and annotated with valuable advice and notes based on practical experience and basics about new forms of assessments that are flexible, continuous, versatile, and authentic. The module 'New trends in teaching engineering mathematics' brings information on how to fully utilize visualization, illustrations and animations in teaching physics or mathematics, in order to unlock their full potential to improve conceptual understanding of complex topics. Presented examples of materials that might be developed using available digital tools serve as inspiration for active teachers eager to improve their teaching methods. What software should be used, and how to introduce it to their own teaching practice for achieving expected results or to develop interesting engaging learning materials might be found in the section 'Use of mathematical software in teaching'.

Conclusions and Implications for STEM Education

The rapid evolution of digital education necessitates continuous research and the ongoing development of educators' digital and pedagogical competences. The DigiSTEM project addressed this need by bringing together the expertise of STEM educators and specialists in online pedagogy to co-create high-quality, openly accessible learning resources. This interdisciplinary collaboration ensured that the developed materials were both technologically current and pedagogically sound. STEM educators contributed practical insights and subject-specific knowledge, while pedagogical experts introduced innovative approaches to digital teaching and learning, particularly in fostering student engagement, self-regulation, and active learning (Deák & Kumar, 2024; Rahman, 2024; Santoveña-Casal & Rodríguez López, 2024). By enhancing digital competences of educators, the DigiSTEM project gives them tools and knowledge to produce and implement digital resources and activities for different personalized learning scenarios in pedagogically meaningful ways.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the EU for supporting this project funded under the ERASMUS+ Program, with reference 2021-1-FI01-KA220-HED-000027535.

References

Deák, C., and Kumar, B. (2024) “A systematic review of STEAM education’s role in nurturing digital competencies for sustainable innovations.” *Education Sciences*, 14(3), pp 226.

Kinnari-Korpela, H. (2019) “Enhancing Learning in Engineering Mathematics Education: Utilising Educational Technology and Promoting Active Learning.” Tampere University. ProGradu-tutkielma.

Kinnari-Korpela, H. and Suhonen, S. (2017) ”How much is too much in e-materials? Case study in engineering.” *EDULEARN17 Proceedings, IATED*, pp 1512-1518.

Rahman, L. (2024) “Pedagogical Approach in STEM Education: A Literature Review.” *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology (ijert)* Volume, 13.

Rinneheimo, K-M., Kinnari-Korpela, H., Velichová, D. and Rasteiro D. (2022) “Promoting Active Learning in STEM Subjects.” In *Towards a new future in engineering education, new scenarios that European alliances of tech universities open up*. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, pp 2329-2331.

Santoveña-Casal, S., and López, S. R. (2024) “Mapping of digital pedagogies in higher education.” *Education and information technologies*, 29(2), pp 2437-2458.